

Monitoring of the Cancer Treatment Process by Temperature Measurements

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Abstract

The usage of temperature measurements in the Magic Light anti-cancer therapy has been investigated in clinical trials for the treatment of Triple Negative Breast Cancer (Invasive Ductal Carcinoma Stage III). Irradiation by RF waves, from the Magic Light device, can increase or decrease the patient's body temperature during one treatment session. It allows for the visualization of the cancer treatment process as well as to monitor its progress.

Treatment of Invasive Ductal Carcinoma (IDC) Stage III, using the Magic Light anti-cancer therapy, was completed and described. The best treatment effect was observed at a frequency of 430 MHz and, applied in turn, at modulation frequencies of 4 kHz, 7 kHz, 10 kHz and 21 kHz and with RF power densities less than 12 mW/cm² at a distance of 1 m from the patient.

The process of cancer treatment using the Magic Light anti-cancer therapy was monitored by measuring the patient's body temperature both before and after each treatment session. A new medical effect was disclosed, which allows the observance of efficiency and progress in the cancer treatment, as well as detecting the presence of cancer cells at the early stages of disease.

In this trial, it was discovered that if cancer is present in the human body, the body temperature after the Magic Light treatment session will always be higher than before this treatment session began. However, if during 5-6 treatment sessions in turn, the body temperature after the treatment session, is lower than it was initially, it means that the cancer has been cured completely.

Temperature measurements using the Magic Light device, may also be used as an oncology test.

Introduction

Temperatures both in the body and in the tumor, reflect physiological and pathological conditions. A reliable, contactless, and simplistic measurement system can be used for long-term monitoring of disease progression and therapy response [1]. Measuring of neoplastic fever in patients with oncology was also described in works [2, 3]. For cancerous tumors, localized temperature variations, both within the tumor and the body, are common due to changes in blood perfusion and metabolic heat generation [1]. In addition to this, inflammation predisposes the development of cancer and promotes all stages of tumor genesis. Cancer cells, as well as surrounding stromal and inflammatory cells, engage in well-orchestrated reciprocal interactions to form an inflammatory tumor microenvironment (TME) [4].

In the present work, the study of the influence of the cancer treatment by the Magic Light device and technology in regard to body temperature, was described in [5, 6 and 7], on the patient's body temperature level before, during and after each treatment session. As was shown in [5], irradiation by the Magic Light device, decreases cells metabolic heat generation and, correspondingly, the cells (and the body's!) temperature.

Nonetheless, in all clinical trials with the treatment of cancer, one can observe another picture. When we measure the body temperature of the patient with cancer by a contactless thermometer, the body temperature after the Magic Light treatment session will always be higher than before this treatment session began. This experimental fact opens a new path to detect the presence of cancer cells within the body, as well as the possibility of observing the cancer

More Information

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treatment efficiency and its results. This is by simply measuring the body temperature before and after, each treatment session during the complete cancer treatment period.

Experimental Part

1. Treatment of Breast Cancer (Triple Negative IDC, Stage III) with the Magic Light Therapy at different regimes.

The method of control for treatment efficiency by temperature measurements before and after each treatment session was tested in clinical trials for treatment of the Triple Negative Invasive Ductal Carcinoma (IDC) Stage III with initial tumor size: 5.5 cm. The results of these clinical trials are presented in Fig. 2, 3 and 4 below.

Patient: Ada (62), ID 322031303, Israel. Diagnose: Triple Negative Invasive Ductal Carcinoma (IDC), Stage III.

Figure 1: Treatment of Cancer by the Magic Light Device (Lab Example)

This case is especially important to consider because triple-negative breast cancer is a kind of breast cancer that does not have any of the receptors that are commonly found in breast cancer. One is for the female hormone estrogen, one is for the female hormone progesterone and one is a protein called human epidermal growth factor (HER2).

If the cancer has any of these three locks, doctors have a few keys (such as hormone therapy or other drugs) they can be used to help destroy the cancer cells. Usually, doctors give a recommendation to have the

lump removed (a *lumpectomy*) or the entire breast removed (a *mastectomy*). However, the treatment for this type of cancer (Triple-negative IDC) using the Magic Light method and device, allows for the curing of this type of cancer without the use of any surgery, chemotherapy, immunotherapy or X-Ray irradiation.

A breast tumor with an initial size of 5.5 cm was decreased, cured and finally disappeared completely during the first month of treatment by the Magic Light device at a frequency modulation of 7 kHz, as was described in [6] and shown in Fig. 2 and Fig. 3. A full and complete cancer treatment was conducted by using a full set of optimal modulation frequencies [7], as is shown in Fig. 4 below.

Protocol of the full cancer treatment

Carrier frequency 430 MHz, frequencies of modulation: 4 KHz, 7 kHz, 10 kHz and 21 kHz, each frequency session was 30 min, one full treatment session was 2 hours, RF power density was less than 12 mW/cm² at a distance from the antenna of approximately 1 m. The time delay between treatment sessions was 48 hours (three times in a week).

Figure 2: Before the Magic Light Treatment

Figure 3: One Month after Start of the Magic Light Treatment

After the tumor disappeared, the experiment with treatment of Triple-Negative IDC Stage III was continued with body temperature measurements taken both before and after each treatment session, as is shown below on Fig. 4. At the conclusion of the experiment, during the final seven sessions, the body temperature was always lower than the initial body temperature, that is, before the session commenced.

Effective modulation frequencies in this case were as follows: 4, 7, 10 and 21 kHz.

Figure 4. Monitoring of the Magic Light Anti-Cancer Therapy by Temperature Measurements of the Patient Body (Ada)

Each modulation frequency was applied for 30 minutes and the time period between each two treatment sessions was 48 hours.

As one can see from temperature measurements in the Part 3 of the Fig. 4, initial body temperatures were higher than temperatures after the treatment session during all the seven final measurements. This means that the cancer was cured completely. As can be seen from Fig. 4 above, the optimal frequencies of modulation for effective treatment of Triple-Negative IDC cancer are following: 4 kHz, 7 kHz, 10 kHz and 21 kHz and they must be applied in turn, for the best and fastest anti-cancer treatment effect. Because this kind of cancer is very aggressive, effective treatment requires using three treatment sessions per week or every 48 hours. The entire process to cure cancer completely, as shown in Fig. 5 above, took three months.

For all patients with cancer, which were cured by the Magic Light method, it is recommended to take a temperature test every six months, as is described above. If the initial body temperature is lower than after the treatment session (even once), the treatment should be continued. The results of a PET-CT scan, performed one year after the start of this cancer treatment with Magic Light anti-cancer therapy, showed a complete absence of any sign of cancer. Further, no negative side effects were observed either during or after the cancer treatment period.

Conclusion

In this work, the best set of modulation frequencies for complete cancer treatment by the Magic Light method

was confirmed. This set consists of the following frequencies of modulation: 4 kHz, 7 kHz, 10 kHz and 21 kHz.

Furthermore, it was also discovered that the human body temperature, after a treatment session, can inform about the treatment process efficiency and its results. When the body temperature after each treatment session was found to be lower than initially and during several following treatment sessions, the cancer was cured completely.

Treatment sessions in the Magic Light anti-cancer therapy also can be used as an oncology test and is much more sensitive than the MRI test.

The optimal required time delay between treatment sessions depends both on the type of cancer and its aggressiveness. For example, for Prostate Adenocarcinoma the time delay was 72 hours (twice a week), for Invasive Ductal Carcinoma (IDC) is 48 hours (three times a week). The same delay can be recommended for Squamous Cell Carcinoma (SCC) and Neuroblastoma.

For Glioma and Glioblastoma, the optimal time delay is 12 hours (twice a day). The optimum time delay for any cancer can be found by measuring the initial body temperature before each treatment session. If this temperature decreases at each following measurement and is close to 36.6 °C, it is optimal. However, if this initial temperature remains at a higher level (for example, 36.9 °C, it indicates that the time delay between the treatment sessions must be decreased in order to cure the cancer completely.

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